

Wheatstone bridge on cantilever PRSA-L300

complete PRSA chip

sensor Wheatstone bridge chip

Cantilever-(CL)-PCB and Counter-Part-(CP)-PCB pinout

Wheatstone bridge schematic

PCB...Printed circuit board